

DETERMINATION OF CHARGE CARRIER SYSTEM PARAMETERS IN $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ BY JOINT ANALYSIS OF TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCES OF FOUR KINETIC COEFFICIENTS

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Abstract

The temperature dependences of electrical conductivity (σ), Hall coefficient (R), thermopower (α), and Nernst–Ettingshausen coefficient (Q) for five $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations in a temperature range of 100–300 K have been studied. According to the obtained experimental data, the temperature dependences of the mobility and the effective scattering parameter have been calculated. The main features of the experimental data can be interpreted in terms of a two-band model of the valence band structure with several groups of holes involved in the transport phenomena. It has been found that the behavior of the temperature dependence of the effective scattering parameter significantly depends on the charge carrier concentration. The determined quantitative values of the effective scattering parameter are consistent with the concepts of a mixed scattering mechanism.

1. Introduction

Semiconductor materials of $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions are commonly used in two main fields of solid-state electronics, namely, infrared optoelectronic devices and thermoelectric converters. The most interesting property of $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ is the ability to control the band gap by changing the chemical composition without a significant change in the crystal structure. In addition, lead chalcogenides are topological insulators; that is, they are representatives of the subclass of narrow-gap semiconductors that act as insulators in the bulk of the material and exhibit metallic conductivity on the surface.

The scientific interest in these materials is primarily associated with their unusual galvanomagnetic, thermomagnetic, and magneto-optic properties.

The solid solution of lead telluride and tin— $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ —is a narrow-gap semiconductor. The band gap of a narrow-gap solid solution is determined by the composition of the solution (x value). At $x = 0.18$, at helium temperatures, the band gap E_g of $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ is about 0.05 eV.

The absolute extremes of the conduction and valence bands of $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ are located at the L point at the boundary of the Brillouin zone. In addition, the valence band of the $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ solid solutions is composed of a group of light and heavy holes.

2. Results and Discussion

To obtain reliable experimental results, severe requirements are imposed on the quality of the samples under study: the volume distribution of the components should be uniform, while the amount of mechanical defects should be reduced to minimum. The most effective method for synthesizing homogeneous $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ single crystals is the gas-phase growth technique.

Experimental studies of transport phenomena in semiconductors provide the most complete information about the kinetics of charge carriers and their energy spectrum with a wide variation in the concentration of charge carriers and impurities and in temperature.

A comprehensive study of the thermopower, electrical conductivity, Hall coefficient, and Nernst–Ettingshausen coefficient (NEC) of the same samples by a joint analysis makes it possible to determine the charge carrier parameters.

In this study, $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ single crystals were synthesized by the gas-phase growth technique. Microstructural and spectral studies and measurements of the Hall coefficient confirmed the high quality of the synthesized single crystals.

Temperature dependences of the kinetic coefficients (thermopower, electrical conductivity, Hall coefficient, and transverse NEC) of the synthesized $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ single crystals with a charge carrier concentration of 10^{16} to 10^{19} cm^{-3} in a temperature range of 80–400 K were studied.

In our previous reports [1, 2], the temperature dependences of thermopower, electrical conductivity, and Hall coefficient were characterized. The temperature studies of electrical conductivity σ , thermopower α , Hall coefficient R , and NEC Q were conducted according to standard procedures.

Measurements of four main kinematic coefficients (σ , R , α , Q) make it possible to determine the main characteristics of a semiconductor material, particularly the effective scattering parameter of charge carriers r_{eff} (exponent in the dependence of the mean free path of the carriers on energy $l \sim \epsilon'$). The effective scattering parameter of carriers r_{eff} can be calculated by the following formula [3–5]:

$$\frac{Q}{R\sigma\alpha} = \frac{r_{\text{eff}} - 0,5}{r_{\text{eff}} + 1} \quad (1)$$

where R is the Hall coefficient, σ is the electrical conductivity, α is the Seebeck coefficient, and Q is the NEC.

Figure 1 shows temperature dependences of the NEC of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations. The temperature dependences of the samples shown in Fig. 1 are nonmonotonic and exhibit a maximum. At low temperatures, the NEC is minimal; with an increase in temperature, it achieves a maximum value and then decreases. An exception is provided by sample 5 (not shown in the figure) with a minimum hole concentration of 10^{16} cm^{-3} ; at low temperatures, the NEC of this sample is maximal and abruptly decreases with increasing temperature. The positive sign of all the NECs suggests that the optical phonon scattering of charge carriers is dominant.

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of the NEC of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations: (2) 15×10^{17} , (3) 5.2×10^{17} , and (4) $2.6 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

The experimental temperature dependences of the Hall coefficient and electrical conductivity of $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ with different charge carrier concentrations are shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

The temperature dependences of the samples shown in Figs. 2 and 3 are nonmonotonic and exhibit a maximum.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of the Hall coefficients of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations: (1) 200×10^{17} , (2) 15×10^{17} , (3) 5.2×10^{17} , (4) 2.6×10^{17} , and (5) $0.52 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 3. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations: (1) 200×10^{17} , (2) 15×10^{17} , (3) 5.2×10^{17} , (4) 2.6×10^{17} , and (5) $0.52 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 4 shows temperature dependences of the thermopower of $\text{Pb}_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{Te}$ ($x = 0.18$) with different charge carrier concentrations. For the samples with a low charge carrier concentration, the thermopower sign inversion is observed; this finding indicates the transition to the intrinsic conductivity region (curves 4, 5). For the samples with a lower charge carrier concentration, the thermopower sign inversion is observed at lower temperatures.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of the thermopower of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations: (2) 15×10^{17} , (3) 5.2×10^{17} , (4) 2.6×10^{17} , and (5) $0.52 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

To interpret the obtained experimental data, the two-band Gottwick's model with a linear temperature term was used [6–9]. In this approximation, it is assumed that the Lorentzian resonance occurs in the vicinity of the Fermi surface. This model makes it possible to determine the Fermi energy and the position and width of the resonance using experimental data. Parameters E_0 and G are determined by the position of the center and the width of the resonance on the energy axis, respectively.

According to the data shown in Figs. 1–4, the temperature dependences of effective scattering parameter r_{eff} can be calculated by formula (1).

Temperature dependences of the effective scattering parameter r_{eff} of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. It is evident from the figures that the behavior of the temperature dependence of the effective scattering parameter significantly depends on the charge carrier concentration.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of the effective scattering parameter r_{eff} of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ samples with different charge carrier concentrations: (2) 15×10^{17} , (3) 5.2×10^{17} , and (4) $2.6 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 6. Temperature dependence of the effective scattering parameter r_{eff} of the $\text{Pb}_{0.82}\text{Sn}_{0.18}\text{Te}$ sample with a charge carrier concentration of $5.2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

It is reasonable to expect that, in addition to acoustic phonon scattering, possible scattering mechanisms will be Coulomb potential scattering of ionized impurities and defects and optical phonon scattering [10].

All the samples are characterized by the following feature: the effective scattering parameter increases with increasing temperature and abruptly decreases upon the achievement of a maximum. For temperatures in a region of 80–250 K, the r_{eff} value is about 0.5; this finding can be attributed to optical phonon scattering. The determined quantitative values of the effective scattering parameter at temperatures above 250 K are consistent with the concepts of a mixed scattering mechanism.

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